

Life

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Life blooms softly when I smile.

Life grows heavy when I cry.

Life dances bright when I play.

Life folds in shadow when I quit.

Life is a wonder when I breathe.

Life is a star when I dream.

Life is a question when I hope.

Life is a storm when I run.

Life is love's flame when I feel.

Life is a heartbeat when I fall.

Life is a mountain when I will.

Life is a prayer when I kneel.

Life is truth's first whisper when I am born—

Yet life is silence, when I die.